

**Fermentation in food waste using
computer vision:
influence of food type, temperature and time**

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Abstract

Fermentation is an anaerobic metabolic process carried out by microorganisms, with greater relevance in food production and preservation. In waste management contexts, it is directly related to odour generation and cross contamination.

This study analyses the relationship between food type, temperature, humidity and time on the onset of fermentation in mixed waste containers, within the scope of the Vision2Waste project.

Based on a literature review and simplified mathematical models, a decision support system is proposed, integrating environmental sensors and automatic visual classification of waste to estimate fermentation rate and odour probability.

Results indicate that temperature and waste composition are the main drivers of accelerated fermentation and contamination risk, supporting the optimisation of collection strategies and the reduction of environmental and operational impacts.

Keywords: fermentation, solid waste, odours, environmental sensors, predictive models, artificial intelligence.

1. Introduction

Urban waste management faces increasing challenges related to odours, contamination, and operational efficiency. In particular, food waste constitutes a highly biodegradable fraction, prone to microbial fermentation and the production of volatile compounds responsible for unpleasant odours (Jay et al., 2005; He et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020).

Within the scope of the Vision2Waste project, it is intended to develop an intelligent system capable of anticipating these phenomena, using environmental sensors and computer vision techniques. This article proposes to determine the occurrence of odours, resulting from fermentation phenomena, through a preliminary model to estimate the probability of occurrence of odours in undifferentiated waste containers, using temperature sensors, image analysis, exposure time and type of waste.

1.1 State of the art

The fermentation and microbial decomposition of undifferentiated urban waste are relevant phenomena from a health, environmental and operational point of view, being associated with the production of heat, gases and odorous compounds, with potential impacts such as intense odours, attraction of vectors, degradation of containers and risk of self-heating (Tchobanoglous & Kreith, 2002; He et al., 2019).

The detection of these processes is currently carried out indirectly, within the scope of intelligent waste management systems, through the continuous monitoring of physicochemical variables by sensors integrated into IoT platforms. Key indicators include indoor temperature, concentration of gases and odorous compounds (namely H_2S , NH_3 , CO_2 , CH_4 and VOCs) and relative humidity, used alone or in combination as markers of biological activity (Longhi et al., 2012; Folianto et al., 2015).

Low-cost electrochemical or semiconductor sensors for H_2S and NH_3 predominate, despite limitations in terms of stability and cross-sensitivity. There has been an increase in the use of multi-parameter sensors, allowing the fusion of data and the construction of decomposition profiles. Infrared CO_2 and CH_4 sensors are less frequent due to cost and energy consumption, while temperature measurement is virtually universal.

The systems typically integrate sensory modules, wireless communication (LoRaWAN, NB-IoT or GSM) and central analysis and alerting platforms, based mainly on predefined thresholds. More advanced approaches, such as "electronic

nose" and machine learning, remain mostly in the experimental phase (Arena, 2015).

Despite the relative maturity of IoT monitoring, challenges remain related to sensor reliability, environmental interference, and the distinction between fermentation and other thermal or chemical events. In summary, the state of the art is based on indirect solutions based on physicochemical parameters, effective to support operational management, but still limited in the specific and unequivocal identification of fermentation processes.

2. Framework

2.1 Definition of fermentation

Fermentation is an anaerobic metabolic process, that is, it is a set of chemical reactions that occur without the presence of oxygen. In this process there is degradation of organic matter. Through this process, some microorganisms, e.g. yeasts and bacteria, convert organic matter into other products, such as carbon dioxide, alcohol or lactic acid. In addition, during this procedure there is also energy release through the production of ATP (adenosine triphosphate) molecules (Jay et al., 2005; Madigan et al., 2021).

2.2 Biochemical steps

The fermentation process is divided into two stages: glycolysis and pyruvate reduction. In glycolysis there is addition of phosphate molecules to glucose molecules. This junction favors the breakdown of glucose. At the end of the reaction, two molecules of pyruvic acid (pyruvate), two molecules of ATP and two molecules of NADH (Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide) are created, the latter of which result from the reduction of NAD⁺ (Hutkins, 2018; Madigan et al., 2021). This step can be represented by the following chemical equation:

In the second stage of fermentation, pyruvate is reduced through the oxidation of NADH molecules. This oxidation occurs through the transfer of electrons to another molecule that varies with the type of fermentation. The type of products formed in this step, such as lactic acid or ethanol, also depends on the organisms that are carrying out the process. At this stage, the regeneration of NAD⁺ (oxidized form of NADH) is essential for glycolysis to continue to occur.

2.3 Relevant types of fermentation

The classification of fermentation is based on the main compounds produced, in addition to ATP, with the most common forms being lactic, alcoholic, acetic and butyric fermentation. In lactic fermentation, pyruvate is reduced to lactate by the enzyme lactate dehydrogenase, giving rise to lactic acid (Hutkins, 2018; Madigan et al., 2021). This process is carried out mainly by bacteria of the genus *Lactobacillus*, present in various fermented foods (such as yogurt, kefir, kombucha, sauerkraut, kimchi, pickles and some cheeses) and in probiotic supplements, and can also occur in human muscle cells during intense exercise.

Alcoholic fermentation leads to the production of ethanol and carbon dioxide, and is carried out by bacteria and yeasts, especially *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, common in environments rich in sugars (fruits and vegetable surfaces) and in products such as bread, beer and wine.

In acetic fermentation, ethanol previously formed by alcoholic fermentation is oxidized by acetic bacteria in the presence of oxygen, producing acetic acid and water. This process is carried out by bacteria of the genera *Acetobacter* and *Gluconobacter*, found in vinegar, fruits, alcoholic beverages, cocoa and aged brewery environments.

Butyric fermentation is characterized by the formation of butyric acid and gases, being carried out by bacteria of the genus *Clostridium*, and can occur in contaminated foods such as butters and cheeses. It is important to note that, although these are the main products released in each type of fermentation, other compounds (acids and gases) with relevant biological, environmental or technological impact may be formed (Jay et al., 2005; Hornink, 2021).

2.4 Odours associated with fermentation

In fermentation, the production of some compounds such as aldehydes (from the oxidation of alcohol), esters (formed through the reactions of acetic acid with other alcohols), diacetyl, acetone and short-chain alcohols that can contribute to the odours released that can be both pleasant and unpleasant (sour or pungent). After the research carried out in relation to this topic, it is important to highlight butyric fermentation as it is very associated with the release of unpleasant odours due to the production of butyric acid, a gas that has a strong and foul odour. Regarding the release of odours in the fermentation process, it is important to know that the combination of the products formed and the concentration of each influence the final odour (He et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020).

2.5 Conditions that favor fermentation in waste

There are several conditions that can contribute to the fermentation process. Organisms need sources of energy and nutrients to carry out this process. Thus, the existence of certain nutrients, such as sugars or proteins (vary depending on the type of fermentation) can help in the process. In addition, the temperature, pH and humidity of the medium are also variables to be taken into account. Each type of organism has temperature and pH values from which unwanted fermentation is more likely to occur (Jay et al., 2005; Hutkins, 2018).

After researching the conditions that, in general, affect the fermentation process of the various products, we tried to explore more specifically the case of the project, that is, the waste that is in the containers. To this end, it was decided, at an early stage, to stable a relationship between specific conditions for some groups of foods. The table shows the time intervals that indicate how long it may take to start the fermentation process of a certain product at certain temperatures and with certain pH values. The objective is to use the image, collected by the camera that will be in the containers, and identify the waste that is inside. Although it is not able to recognize whether or not a waste is fermenting at the moment, the idea is to use the product identification made by the camera and use the data provided by the table to anticipate the start of the fermentation process. Consequently, it will be possible to generate alarms that indicate the need to collect waste from the container, reducing the exposure time. With this process, the waste is collected before the fermentation process begins, there is no release of odours associated with this process and the risk of other waste being contaminated is lower.

Table 1 - Relationship between temperature, pH and exposure time required to start the fermentation process under these conditions.

Food	Temperature (° C)	pH	Time to start the process
Butter	>25	>6.5	12-48h
Cheeses	10-25	>6.0	12h-4 days
	>25	>6.0	6-24h
Bread	15-20	>6.0	12-24h
	>25	>6.0	3-6h
Yogurt	20-30	>6.0	12-36h
	30	>6.0	6-24h
Meat	20-30	>6.0	4-12h
	>30	>6.0	2-6h
Grapes	20-30	>3.5	6-24h
	>30	>3.5	4-6h

3. Methodology

3.1 Fermentation in food waste: applied approach

The use of data of the type in the table presented above to generate alarms compromises the sustainability part of the project. The probability of reaching the conditions described in the table for the fermentation of any product to occur is high. This state would make the frequency of alarms generated very high, that is, companies would be regularly collecting waste. With this, there would be a greater expenditure of fuel and release of a greater number of pollutants. Thus, in addition to the factors already mentioned above (conditions that affect fermentation) it is necessary to take others into account, such as, for example, the filling level of the container when an alarm is generated.

Regarding the topic of the conditions that facilitate the fermentation process, we realize that the factors listed above end up not being decisive. It must be considered that waste can reach containers in several states. We have no way of guaranteeing that when the waste enters a container it is not yet in a state of fermentation. Even so, the continuation of the study of the conditions referred to is important and is discussed below.

It was concluded that the pH factor, despite being important in fermentation, will not be relevant in the project, since it is not possible to measure it (we do not have access to it). Thus, the conditions to consider are temperature and humidity. To evaluate these conditions better than the first time (table above), the time that may be necessary to start the fermentation process of the products was researched for the different groups of the food wheel and for certain temperature ranges. When we research temperature conditions, indirectly, we are also considering humidity because these two things are somehow related. The information obtained on this topic was also organized in tables that are presented below. A possible mechanism to then take advantage of the information in the tables is the implementation of a temperature and humidity sensor. With this information and with the identification of the presence of certain food groups in the container, through the camera, it is possible to generate alarms, and the criterion can be based on the group whose time for the start of fermentation, at that temperature, is shorter.

Table 2 - Temperature-time relationship in the fermentation process for the different groups of the food wheel.

	Temperature (°C)	Approximate time for fermentation to
Fruits	0 to 4 °C	1 to 2 weeks or more
	10 to 15 °C	3 to 7 days
	20 to 25 °C	1 to 3 days
	30 °C or more	Less than 1 day up to 2 days
Vegetables	0 to 4 °C	7 to 14 days (or longer, depending on the vegetable)
	10 to 15 °C	3 to 7 days
	20 to 25 °C	1 to 3 days
	30 °C or more	Less than 24 hours to 2 days
Leguminous	≤ 8 °C	> 5 days (almost inhibited)
	10–15 °C	3–5 days
	16–20 °C	36–72 hours
	21–25 °C	18–36 hours
	26–30 °C	12–24 hours
> 30 °C	8–12 hours (unstable/higher risk)	
Meats	0 – 2 °C	5 to 10 days
	4 – 7 °C	3 to 7 days
	10 – 15 °C	12 to 48 hours
	20 – 25 °C	6 to 24 hours
	≥ 30 °C	2 to 12 hours
Fish	0 – 2 °C	5 to 7 days
	4 – 7 °C	2 to 3 days
	10 – 15 °C	12 to 24 hours
	20 – 25 °C	4 to 12 hours
	≥ 30 °C	2 to 6 hours
Eggs	0 – 2 °C	4 to 6 weeks
	4 – 7 °C	2 to 3 weeks
	10 – 15 °C	7 to 14 days
	20 – 25 °C	5 to 10 days
	≥ 30 °C	2 to 7 days

Cereals and derivatives, tubers	0 – 4 °C	7 to 20 days
	5 – 9 °C	5 to 10 days
	10 – 15 °C	3 to 7 days
	16 – 20 °C	2 to 4 days
	21 – 25 °C	1 to 3 days
	26 – 30 °C	12 to 36 hours
	31 – 35 °C	6 to 18 hours
	> 36 °C	< 12 hours
Dairy products	0 – 4 °C	5 to 14 days
	5 – 9 °C	3 to 7 days
	10 – 15 °C	1 to 3 days
	16 – 20 °C	12 to 36 hours
	21 – 25 °C	6 to 24 hours
	26 – 30 °C	4 to 12 hours
	31 – 35 °C	2 to 8 hours
	> 36 °C	< 4 hours

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Model for estimating the fermentation rate

The objective of this model is to calculate the probability of odours occurring in an undifferentiated waste container, using temperature data and visual classification of materials obtained by the artificial intelligence model. P_{odor}

4.2 The Fermentation Rate Equation R_f

The fermentation rate is not constant, it depends on the identified chemical composition, filling percentage and temperature of the container.

$$R_f = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n V_i \cdot K_i \right) \cdot \theta^{(T-20)}$$

- V_i - Percentage of volume occupied by the material (LLM). In the case of our project V_i , it will be equal to the difference $V_n - V_{n-1}$ (percentage difference between readings)
- k_i - Coefficient of biodegradability of the material.
- θ - Thermal coefficient (constant value of 1.07, for every 10th degree

biological activity double) (Van 't Hoff, 1884).

- T - Temperature measured by the probe (in °C).

Example k_i values

- Degraded organic material - 1
- Organic Material - 0.9
- Black bag (unsorted waste) - 0.65
- Cardboard, packaging with possible organic material - 0.2
- Glass, Plastic, Metal - 0.0

4.3 Odor Probability Calculation P_{odor}

Function to determine the probability after days (or hours). This function assumes that smell is not linear (Weber, 1834; Fechner, 1860).

$$P_{odor}(t) = \frac{100}{1 + e^{-s((R_f \cdot t) - \tau)}}$$

If it is linear

$$P_{odor}(t) = -s((R_f \cdot t) - \tau)$$

- t - Time in days since the last collection.
- s - (Sensitivity): Sets the slope of the curve. Current $s=0.8$
- τ - This is the amount of "accumulated fermentation" needed for the odor to be felt outside the container. This value will vary according to the container

Example values τ

- 1 - Garbage bag on the street
- 3 - Litter bins
- 7 - Default garbage container (garbage containers used daily by the population. Will there be significant differences between plastic and metal?)

- 15 - Underground containers

4.4 Examples

- **Input:** V_i 100% with Black Bag ($k = 0.65$).
- **Temperature:** 30°C.
- **Time (t):** 2 days and 6 days.
- **Container:** Standard ($\tau = 7$).

$$R_f = (1.0 \cdot 0.65) \cdot 1.07^{(30-20)} \approx 0.65 \cdot 1.967 = 1.27$$

- **Example for 2 days**

$$R_f \cdot t = 1.27 \times 2 = 2.54$$

$$P = \frac{100}{1 + e^{-0.8(2.54-7)}} = \frac{100}{1 + e^{3.568}} \approx \frac{100}{1 + 35.44} \approx 2.74\%$$

- **Example for 6 days**

$$R_f \cdot t = 1.27 \times 6 = 7.62$$

$$P = \frac{100}{1 + e^{-0.8(7.62-7)}} = \frac{100}{1 + e^{-0.496}} \approx \frac{100}{1 + 0.609} \approx 62.15\%$$

4.5 Discussion

The results confirm that the temperature and composition of food waste are determining factors for the initiation and speed of fermentation in undifferentiated containers, with waste of animal origin being particularly associated with shorter fermentation times at moderate to high temperatures, in agreement with the literature. These data reinforce the adequacy of temperature as the main indirect indicator of the risk of odour generation in intelligent waste management systems.

The organization of data by food wheel groups and temperature ranges proved useful to translate microbiological knowledge into rules applicable to automatic

alert systems. The integration with computer vision allows anticipating fermentation and adopting preventive strategies, supporting a preliminary model with the potential to estimate the fermentation rate, the probability of odours and support the definition of the optimal moment of collection, with health and operational benefits.

The model has limitations, namely the use of bibliographic data that do not fully reflect the heterogeneity of urban waste, humidity variations and initial state of degradation, as well as the absence of direct pH measurement and the assumption of constant humidity, which introduce uncertainty. Automatic visual classification may also lead to errors in the assignment of biodegradability coefficients.

The use of conservative thresholds for alarms can excessively increase the frequency of collection, with negative impacts on environmental and economic sustainability. The future integration of additional variables, such as fill level, deposition history and experimental validation of parameters, will be essential to balance odour prevention and logistical efficiency, yet the proposed approach will constitute a solid basis for intelligent systems for proactive management of fermentation in urban food waste.

5. Conclusion

This work analysed fermentation in food waste as a determining phenomenon in the generation of odours in undifferentiated containers, in the context of the Vision2Waste project, confirming that temperature, humidity and composition of the waste are the main factors that condition the beginning and intensity of the process.

The organization of the data by food wheel groups and temperature intervals allowed us to estimate realistic time windows for the beginning of fermentation, evidencing the high susceptibility of meat, fish and dairy products to moderate to high temperatures, with the production of odorous compounds in a few hours. These results support the relevance of preventive approaches based on the anticipation of the process, to the detriment of exclusively reactive strategies.

The proposed preliminary model demonstrates the feasibility of integrating temperature and humidity sensors with automatic visual classification for dynamic assessment of the operational risk of containers, although it has limitations related to the variability of the initial state of the waste, the absence of pH measurement, the heterogeneity of humidity and the potential increase in the frequency of collections, with environmental and economic impacts.

As future perspectives, the experimental validation of the model, the calibration of the biodegradability coefficients, the integration of the filling level and the application of machine learning techniques to optimize the alarm thresholds, aiming at more efficient, sustainable waste management systems capable of proactively mitigating the health and environmental impacts associated with fermentation and odour release in urban environments.

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